

**AN ASSESSMENT STUDY OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP BUSINESS MODELS TO KNOW THEIR
IMPACT ON SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT OF WOMEN EVEN DURING AMID
ECONOMIC CRISIS RESULTED DUE TO COVID-19** □ Mr. Arvind Kumar Singh*
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ABSTRACT

“When going gets tough, the tough get going”, Social enterprise business models truly signifies this saying in current scenario. Even sharing half of world population, women are always being neglected in families, societies, countries and globally and treated as subordinate of their counterpart Gender men. This study focuses to access how social enterprises models are helpful in economic empowerment of their member women beneficiaries and also try to reveal that how social entrepreneurship business models are vital not only for women empowerment only but also global crisis like COVID-19. This research study is conducted using Pragmatic research approach, Descriptive research design with mixed method for quantitative and qualitative data analysis. The result of this study reveals that social enterprise membership help underprivileged women to get better control and access over financial resources, which leads them to gain self-dependency and economic soundness and also vital for society to fight against unprecedented global crisis like novel corona virus.

Keywords : Social Entrepreneurship, Women Economic-empowerment, COVID-19 economic crisis

Introduction -

During this corona virus crisis' when all the economics of the world have been suffering with significant dip down and people are crippling with many severe problems like starving from hunger, medical issues and many of business houses have been shut down and millions of individuals have to lose their employment and majority of jobs are also at stake. Since India is a developing economy and majority of our population comes below the poverty line, Although Governments are trying their level best to cope up with this unprecedented crisis however their efforts are not sufficient to recover from this misery. At this tough time social entrepreneurial efforts are clearly coming out to help needy people with both their hands. Social firms are arranging food, shelter, and personal hygiene for deprived one. This study aims to elucidate the efforts made by the selected social Enterprises in Lucknow, providing the affordable solution in form of food and

safety kit to support UP government to fight against COVID-19 crisis and on the other side also generating sustainable livelihood for their female beneficiaries to safeguard their economic means.

Problem Statement-

Because of Corona Crisis it has been estimated that India's GDP were downsized indeed more too negative figures, flagging a profound subsidence. Inside a month, unemployment rose from 6.7% on 15 March 2020 to 26% on 19 April 2020. Amid the lockdown, an assessed 14 corer individuals have lost livelihoods. This study try to explores, in this catastrophic situation how these SEE's serve the community and generate economic means for their dependents to meet out their expenses.

Objective of Study –

The prime objective of this study is study to access the economic empowerment status of women beneficiaries of selected social enterprises working in Lucknow city and its nearby vicinity.

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Significance of Study –This study is relevant because this can be used for various social organization and business venture and government also to understand how then can establish sustainability in organization to generate employment for their employee at one side and also can provide services to community to meet out with these adverse circumstances. **Limitation of Study**- Primary data for this research is collected from women beneficiaries of few social Enterprises providing their services in Lucknow city and also due to lockdown situation data was collected through emails and telephonic conversation and scope of these research findings is confined to a city level. **Review of Literature** - The term 'entrepreneur' got its specific importance from Jean Baptiste in the nineteenth century, when he expressed that the entrepreneur is person who shifts economic assets from a zone of lower to a vicinity of better performance and greater outstanding yields.

The conceptual framework of entrepreneurship is being established on the divergent trade hones and results of entrepreneurial endeavours. It does not target only to accomplish wealth, getting rich and generate employment opportunity but on broader vision, entrepreneurship focuses on institutional, economic upswing, social and cultural domain connected to a region, state, country or global economy.

Kao (1993) defines entrepreneurship as the way toward including something new making use of innovativeness, creativeness and something which ingenious to create riches for the individual and improving society. Gobbi et al. (2005) narrowed it down and illustrate, entrepreneurship as a process to establish or expand a micro enterprises or venture operate by an entrepreneur who should be in position to appoint minimum five people and get the business operation done through them. Precisely we can understand entrepreneurship as an innovation profession which plays vital role in growth of individuals, society, states, nations and economies.

It is not certain when concept of social entrepreneurship was coined first but precisely we may say that in year 1954 first time Professor William N. Parker elucidate this concept in his scholarly article

published in The Journal of Economic History where he talk about various perspective of entrepreneurship in German aspect. The phenomenon "social entrepreneurship" has increased greater prominent reputé and visibility from 1990s because off exemplary contribution made by numerous scholars in their writing.

Thompson et al. (2000) describes Social entrepreneurs are individuals who take initiative to acquire collectively the important resources (typically human beings, frequently volunteers, money, and premises) and use these to “make a difference” in society. Precisely Social entrepreneurs are those who take up most pressing and ignored problems of society, convert them into business opportunity generate employment and revenue while giving most importance to social welfare.

Social entrepreneurship is an entrepreneurial act done by a social entrepreneur. According to Dees, J. G. (1998), Scholarly writing distinguish commercial entrepreneurship from social entrepreneurship on the doctrine of in particular what persuades these commercial enterprise visionaries – with conventional commercial enterprise owners incited on by means of cash and social enterprise firms governed by applying social mission-related effect. We can outline Social enterprises is an entrepreneurial avenue for transmitting social issues placing efforts to gain social functions and creating exemplary community change.

Women are approximately 50% of total global population and nearly apportionment 48% in population of India. However even sharing approximately half of the total world population, women are always being neglected in families, societies, countries and globally. They are treated as weaker section in community. As per one study of World Bank in 2011, women are responsible to share 66% of total world work load, involve in generation of 50% food stuff but only get 10% from total global pay-out and sadly enjoy only 1% of ownership in global property.

Empowerment is a process of providing strength to weaker section, first time this terminology was mentioned by Scholar Paulo Freire in his book published in year 1968 named 'Pedagogy of the Oppressed' . Khanday, Shah, Mir, & Rasool, (2015) said that

Empowerment can be interpreted as a phenomena comprising diversified aims, varied layer and multi-dimensional dimensions. Kabeer (2012) defined empowerment as the amplification of people's abilities to develop strategic life choices. Different scholars have applied various dimensions and terms for explaining empowerment however majority of them has given weightage to economic, social, gender, democratic and cultural empowerment.

The slogan "Empowerment of women" was first buzzed at the World Conference on Women organised in Mexico City during June 9 to July 2, 1975 and theme of the convocation was harmonises with the International Year of Women (1975), making it clear that they are reminding the global community that the problem of abuse and disparity has been a persistent problem in most of the world.

Kabeer, (2001) defines women's empowerment as developing a woman's ability to resolve important life decisions in self-denying situations and to resolve important life decisions. Women's ability to make strategic decisions is their activity for agency.

Key terminology used in many studies by scholars are include selection, selection, agency, control and force however majority of academic erudite have signifies the importance of economic power and access for women empowerment.

Strong M. (2007) explains to Economic empowerment as ability of women and men to engage in the participation and development process that recognizes and acknowledges the value of their contribution honours their dignity and makes it possible to interact and distribution of development benefits. Dufflow, E. (2012) explains about strong link between economic growth and women's empowerment. Women advancement plays significant role in reducing the imbalance between men and women and women's participation in economic activities can lead to growth.

Precisely we may say that empowered women must be equipped to involve in decision making process. Social entrepreneurship can be understood as one of key methods which play the significant role in empowering women.

Significance of Social Entrepreneurship in battle with COVID-19 crisis

As we all aware that unprecedented pandemic COVID-19 is biggest challenge in front of world and this virus has impacted almost every sphere of this globe. The International Labour Organization (ILO) has raised the concern of sharp decline in the ability to sustain workforce as a result of this pandemic of economies and it is threatening the livelihood of 1.6 billion workers who are part of the informal economy eventually which is half of global workforce.

The COVID-19 epidemic highlights systemic discrepancies in our global economic system and threatens progress toward the promotion of equality and human rights. Social entrepreneurs solve market and government failures by excluding and serving the weakest, most affected by the effects of this Pandemic.

Ashoka foundation and Schwab foundation two of the biggest chain of global social entrepreneurs have strategic their resources to fight up against COVID-19 crises.

On one hand Schwab foundation has launched a global alliance name "COVID Response Alliance for Social Entrepreneurs" where 40 renowned global organizations are collaboratively supporting more than 15,000 social entrepreneurs in world to bring about a "social economy". Ashoka foundation has also created an alliance between its member global social entrepreneurs named "Catalist-2030" during the period of COVID-19, aims to collective response all most pressing problems and challenges of global society and corona crisis is one of them. This alliance work on three step strategy to solve the societal problems – i) Coordinate Change ii) Facilitate system change iii) Optimise funding system

Research Methodology

This research targets to gather both quantitative and qualitative information so **Pragmatic research approach** and **Mixed method** has been used, **Descriptive** and **diagnostic research design** is been implemented. **Purposive Random sampling** method is used to collect the data from population of **80 respondents** of **two social enterprises** located in

Lucknow city and SPSS 20 software has been used for data analysis.

Data Analysis and Key finding

Research Hypothesis Testing

H0¹: Social Enterprises have no significant impact on achieving basic material needs and to increase their productive resources to empower them economically (Null hypothesis)

H1¹: Social Enterprises have significant impact on achieving basic material needs and to increase their productive resources to empower them economically (Test Hypothesis)

The objective is to find out the significant impact on the coverage of the basic material requirements and to increase the production resources of the respondents who are female beneficiaries of chosen social enterprises, Response were collected from 80 respondents.

Paired Samples Statistics					
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	State your Monthly Income (Before Joining SEE)	2.52	66	1.140	.140
	State your Monthly Income (After Joining SEE)	3.12	66	.795	.098
Pair 2	State your Expenditure Incurred on the following before Joining/ Membership of Social Enterprise -	2.74	80	.990	.111
	State your Expenditure Incurred on the following after Joining/ Membership of Social Enterprise -	3.05	80	.654	.073
Pair 3	Eco_emp_pre (Access and control over financial assets)	.43	80	.253	.028
	Eco_emp_post Access and control over financial assets)	.69	80	.228	.026

Paired sample t test has been done to check the impact on monthly income, monthly expenses and assess and control over financial asset of the respondents on pre and post joining social enterprises. Mean value for monthly income has moved from pre to post- **2.52 to 3.12** and which has also impacted the expenditures of basic

needs and this mean value was also moved from pre to post membership- **2.74 to 3.14** and women beneficiaries (respondents) have also gain better access on Financial Asset and property from pre membership to post membership here also mean value has significantly increased from- **.43 to .69**

Paired Samples Correlations				
		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	State your Monthly Income (Before Joining SEE) & State your Monthly Income (After Joining SEE)	66	.643	.000
Pair 2	State your Expenditure Incurred on the following before Joining/ Membership of Social Enterprise - State your Expenditure Incurred on the following after Joining/ Membership of Social Enterprise	80	.235	.036
Pair 3	Eco_emp_pre & Eco_emp_post (Access and control over financial assets)	80	.255	.023

In comparison on pre and post membership monthly income a positive correlation of **.643** was found at P Value **.000** and for the case of pre and post membership monthly expenditure of basic needs also a

positive correlation of **.235** was found at P Value **.036** and there was also a positive correlation between pre and post membership control and access on financial asset was **.255** at a P Value of **.023**

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	State your Monthly Income (Before Joining SEE) - State your Monthly Income (After Joining SEE)	-.606	.875	.108	-.821	-.391	5.627	65	.000

Pair 2	State your Expenditure Incurred on the following before Joining/ Membership of SEE – State your Expenditure Incurred on the following after Joining/ Membership of SEE-	-.313	1.051	.117	-.546	-.079	2.661	79	.009
Pair 3	Eco_emp_pre - Eco_emp_post	-.269	.294	.033	-.334	-.203	8.165	79	.000

Interpretation: As per the results from paired t-test p-value for all three variables before and after joining membership of social enterprise is significant for income level it is (p-value 0.00, <0.05), for expenditures of basic needs it is (p-value 0.009, <0.05), and access and control over financial Assets it is (p-value 0.00, <0.05), which means there is a significant impact in the income level, expenditure on monthly basic needs and financial asset of the respondents on post joining social enterprises. Hence **Test hypothesis is accepted and null hypothesis is rejected.**

Finding of Frequency Analysis-

1. Age of Respondents-

Age	Freq.	Valid%	Cum%
20 to 30 years	28	35.0%	35.0%
31 to 40 years	22	27.5%	62.5%
41 to 50 years	23	28.8%	91.3%
> 50 years	7	8.8%	100.0%
Total	80	100.0%	

2. Education of Respondents-

Educational Qualification	Freq.	Valid%	Cum%
Illiterate	12	15.0%	15.0%
Literate	18	22.5%	37.5%
Primary	16	20.0%	57.5%
Secondary	7	8.8%	66.3%
Higher Secondary	16	20.0%	86.3%
Post Graduate	11	13.8%	100%
Total	80	100.0%	

3. Association with SEE as-

Association with Enterprise	Freq.	Valid%	Cum%
Full time Employee	21	26.3%	26.3%
Part time Employee	18	22.5%	48.8%
Direct Beneficiary	16	20.0%	68.8%
Linked Beneficiary	18	22.5%	91.3%
Others	7	8.8%	100.0%
Total	80	100.0%	

4. Working/membership duration with enterprise-

Working/attached with Social Enterprise	Freq.	Valid%	Cum%
Less than 6 months	16	20.0%	20.0%
6 months-2 Years	24	30.0%	50.0%
2 to 5 years	30	37.5%	87.5%
More than 5 years	10	12.5%	100.0%
Total	80	100.0%	

5. Monthly Family Income-

Monthly Income of Family	Freq.	Valid%	Cum%
< 5000/-	8	10.0%	10.0%
5001/- to 15,000/-	42	52.5%	62.5%
15001/- to 25,000/-	15	18.8%	81.3%
> 25000/-	15	18.8%	100.0%
Total	80	100.0%	

6. Do you earn for your family and if yes then main source of your earnings-

Do you work to earn for yourself and Family	Main Source of Your Earning	Freq.	Valid%	Cum%
No	(blank)	14	18%	18%
No Total		14	18%	
Yes	Farming Activity	12	15%	33%
	Business Income	15	19%	51%
	Salary Income	35	44%	95%
	Others	4	5%	100%
Yes Total		66	83%	
Grand Total		80	100%	

7. State your monthly income before and after getting membership of enterprise-

Do you work to earn for yourself and Family	Before Joining	Freq.	Valid%	Cum%
No	(blank)	14	18%	18%
No Total		14	18%	
Yes	Below Rs. 2000	14	18%	35%
	2001-5000	24	30%	65%
	5001-10000	8	10%	75%
	Above 10000	20	25%	100%
Yes Total		66	83%	
Grand Total		80	100%	

Do you work to earn for yourself and Family	After Joining	Freq.	Valid%	Cum%
No	(blank)	14	18%	18%
No Total		14	18%	
Yes	Below Rs. 2000	3	4%	21%
	2001-5000	8	10%	31%
	5001-10000	33	41%	73%
	Above 10000	22	28%	100%
Yes Total		66	83%	
Grand Total		80	100%	

8. Monthly Expenditures on basic needs before and after joining membership of Enterprise-

Before Membership	Freq.	Valid%	Cum%
Below Rs. 2000	13	16.3%	16.3%
2001-5000	13	16.3%	32.5%
5001-10000	36	45.0%	77.5%
Above 10000	18	22.5%	100.0%
Total	80	100.0%	

After Membership	Freq.	Valid%	Cum%
Below Rs. 2000	2	2.5%	2.5%
2001-5000	9	11.3%	13.8%
5001-10000	52	65.0%	78.8%
Above 10000	17	22.2%	100.0%
Total	80	100.0%	

Revenue Sources/Methods of Social enterprises during COVID-19 Crises-

Over telephonic interview it was revealed by the key officials of both the organisations that just like all other businesses and economies, their revenue sources have also been affected badly and it has become difficult to arrange frequent livelihood for their female beneficiaries. These organisations have found their solution out of the problem, with the help of donation and charity from few organizations who are supposed to their existing client in CSR funds and few individuals they have started to make affordable meals on their behalf (Clients) for migrants' labours, supplying through community kitchen established by UP government and also supplying meals through clients supervisors. To arrange livelihood for their works these organisation had also stitched affordable good quality cotton face mask and gloves for supply it to corporate house works and client charity distribution.

During the lockdown period these organisations have prepared and distributed near about 2.15 lacs meals and also made and sold approximately 30 thousand cotton masks & cotton gloves.

Conclusion-

As Swami Vivekananda quoted rightly "There is no chance for the welfare of the world unless the condition of woman is improved. It is not possible for a bird to fly on only one wing". Since women magnitudes on half of global population, so we cannot have a better world if we do not take women empowerment movement religiously. In this study this attempt was made to understand that whether membership of social enterprise businesses (independent variable) is helpful for

economic empowerment of women (dependent variable) or not and how this business model can be a vital resource to generate sustainable employment even in unprecedented crisis like COVID-19. The results of this study demystify that after joining membership of Social enterprises there is a significant increase in monthly income of respondents and they are also become more capable to meet-out their basic monthly expenditure and also able to upgrade their living standard. Now many Researchers and Agencies have accepted in their academia that Social Entrepreneurship business model is an effective method for gearing up women empowerment movement spread and this study also concludes that social entrepreneurial efforts are essential for global fight against unprecedented crisis like COVID-19.

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